

Information Communication Technological (ICT) Values for The Changing Higher Education Scenario

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Abstract- The influence of the information and communication technologies (ICTs) in open and distance learning (ODL) in a developing country is critically evaluated in this paper. The Empowering Values of Technology assumes significance here, which can be achieved only through fostering ICT values among the students. There is transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the learner a one-way process that places the learner at the 'receiving end'. Teachers enjoy being looked up as know-it-all. Today the globe has shrunk into a tiny village and the entire globe scenario has been brought onto a tiny screen under the click of a mouse button. Literacy in the 21st Century is going to be understood as computer literacy. If knowledge is power. Information Technology provides the means of knowledge. Information Technology Values have become essential for the new educator; who has to deal with a new student, in a new school, using new medium, namely the Internet in a new learning environment with free access to a large amount of information resources. It extends far beyond familiarity and facility with techniques within ICT such as clicking on the right buttons to use a word processor, spreadsheet or the Internet and encompasses a critical engagement with the appropriate use of ICT. It implies an understanding, not only of the features of ICT which support an activity in teaching and learning, but also of the ways in which working practices and knowledge within a subject context can be changed or developed.

Key Words: Information Technology, provides Knowledge, Essential Values, understood Computer Literacy.

Introduction:

Today the globe has shrunk into a tiny village and the entire globe scenario has been brought onto a tiny screen under the click of a mouse button. Literacy in the 21st Century is going to be understood as computer literacy. If knowledge is power. Information Technology provides the means of knowledge. Information Technology Values have become essential for the new educator, who has to deal with a new student, in a new school, using new medium, namely the Internet in a new learning environment with free access to a large amount of information resources.

Prologue

The prevailing higher education system subscribes to the 'banking concept' the concept that the teacher is a repository of (all) knowledge and its sole dispenser, and the learner the recipient. There is transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the learner a one-way process that places the learner at the 'receiving end'. Teachers enjoy being looked up as know-it-all. And the learner's expectations have, through the ages, got conditioned accordingly. This is doubly disempowering it breeds learner dependence, and incapacitates them, indirectly damaging their self-confidence. They begin grossly underestimating their cognitive resourcefulness. They cannot believe that they carry with them knowledge and experience. The Empowering Values of Technology assumes significance here, which can be achieved only through fostering ICT values among the students.

ICT values as a tool of learner empowerment

The world has witnessed several information revolutions in the past. The first one was 6000 years ago when writing was invented. The second information revolution was in 1300 B.C when the first written book was published. The third information revolution was triggered by the invention of the printing press in 1455 AD. Every invention has improved productivity and has enhanced the standard of living of the mankind. We are now witnessing the fourth information revolution the ICT revolution. Today the globe has shrunk into a tiny village and the entire globe scenario has been brought onto a tiny screen under the click of a mouse button. Literacy in the 21st Century is going to be understood as computer literacy. If knowledge is power. Information Technology provides the means of knowledge.

'UNESCO considered Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as "scientific, technological and engineering disciplines and the management techniques used in information handling and processing, their application, computers and their interaction with men and machines, and associated social, economical and cultural matters". The advent of Information on the matrix of Socio-economic activity the world over, It is transforming the way people do things all things.

Industrial and developing countries alike are formulating policies and programmes to accelerate its development, diffusion and empowerment abilities. The world's developed governments are rocketing ahead in formulating, developing and implementing a variety of national policies and synergic government public programmes to exploit the enormous unfathomed benefits, of this Fourth Information Revolution, Developing countries like India having sensed it, are galloping at a breakneck velocity for establishing and capitalizing on the enabling capabilities of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Thanks to Information Technology, new values are emerging in the educational scenario of the current context.

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realizing this importance of Information Technology, the ICT education in India is being incorporated as a part of the academic curriculum in schools, college and universities. At the school level, the basics of Information Technology and Training on computer usage are focused upon to make the outgoing schoolchildren ICT literate. At the college and university levels, the studies of ICT applications in all disciplines are focused.

The human brain has the privileged faculties of thinking, imagination and creativity. The computer can store a vast amount of information but it cannot think. It will, therefore, be an anachronism to continue to use the human brain for memorizing information when it should be used for solving problems, creative thinking the skill attributes of knowledge workers. Therefore, any system of education unless it is learner centered, is around developing thinking skills and is able to help learners in acquiring the ability of learning how to learn will gradually lost its relevance. Hence, the role of the teacher shall now be visualized by Sri Aurobindo as far back as in 1910:

“The first principle of true teaching is that nothing. Can be taught. The teacher is not an instructor or taskmaster; he is a helper and a guide. His business is to suggest a not to impose. He does not actually he the pupils” mind; he only shows him how to perfect bs instruments of joie an Pea Gan him in the process. He does not actually train the pupils mind he only shows him how to perfect his instrument of knowledge to him .He shows him how to acquire knowledge or how to acquire the knowledge for himself .He does not call for that is within; he only shows him where it lies and how be habituated to rise to the surface”.

Delors’ Commission Report : In the Delors Commission Report *Learning the Treasure Within* (1996). Aurobindo’s thoughts seem to have been reiterated.” Teachers must adapt their relationship with learners, switching roles from ‘soloist’ to accompanist; an shifting the emphasis from dispensing information to helping learners seek, organize and manage knowledge, guiding them rather than molding them “maintaining quality. The possibilities they open up, along with their advantages for teaching, are vast. Computers and multimedia systems, for instance, make it possible to design individual learning paths along which each pupil can move at his or her own pace; they also make it easier for teachers to organize acquisition in mixed ability classes”.

Empowering higher education learners through ‘ICT values’

Developing ICT values is a challenging and stimulating aspect of teaching. The word ‘capability ‘implies and understanding of the purpose and fitness of a task; a confidence and competence to undertake an activity; and ability to evaluate and reflect upon the situation and be open to further developments.

It extends far beyond familiarity and facility with techniques within ICT such as clicking on the right buttons to use a word processor, spreadsheet or the Internet and encompasses a critical engagement with the appropriate use of ICT: It implies an understanding, not only of the features of ICT which support an activity in teaching and learning, but also of the ways in which working practices and knowledge within a subject context can be changed or developed. It encompasses a conceptual understanding of the ways in which information is organized, accessed, presented and communicated with these technologies.

ICT values, it is a useful

When thinking about ICT values, it is a useful exercise to imagine the learner in a classroom in which you have observed or worked. Picture them using ICT in the classroom; at home; with their peers; in their leisure and entertainment; in their interactions with the world outside. Think about the ways in which they might use digital technologies as they develop in the next five, ten, fifteen and twenty years. How would you like to imagine them using the technology to express their ideas and opinions; to appreciate and understand the connections between themselves and the rest of the world; to celebrate their individuality and the individuality of others? How might they are ICT to be curious and to look at things from alternative perspectives? How might ICT play a role in helping them to become confident and self-motivated; to be inspired to work with spirit and imagination; to make decisions, which might be collaborative an difficult? How do you envisage learners being able to use digital technologies to provide opportunities for interactions between people, ideas, space and time? How might the use of ICT encourage risk-taking and explorations?

How your notions of literacy might be extended by the ways of ‘reading’ and ‘writing’ we develop with ICT? What are your images of the times and places where learners learn? What are your images of the roles that teachers play as learners develop ICT capability? If we consider ICT values in the context of our values and beliefs about he purposes and practice of education, we can see that the technology is not a neutral collection of equipment an connections, but inculcates certain values as part of a complex interaction between people.

ICT prepares pupils to participate in a rapidly changing world in which work and other activities are increasingly transformed by access to varied and developing technology. Pupils use ICT to fin, explore, analyse, exchange and present information responsibly, creatively and with discrimination. They learn how to employ ICT to enable rapid access to ideas and experiences from a wide range of people, communities and cultures. Increased capability in the use of ICT promotes initiative and independent learning with pupils being able to make informed judgments about when and where to use ICT to best effect and to consider its implications for home and work, both now and in the future. Empowering learners to develop ICT values far more challenging then teaching a series of techniques in applications, which will soon be redundant in a fast changing context. We can use ICT not only as passive consumers and collectors of information, but also as people who are collaborative, creative and able to make critical choices. The ways in which we approach ICT values can be reflection of our own values and beliefs about what it means to learn and to teach in

an information society. To conclude, the best and most effective teaching practice to empower the Learner is through developing ICT values among the learners.

ICT-Based Higher Education / Online Education

In recent times factors have emerged which have strengthened and encouraged moves to adapt ICTs into classrooms and learning settings. There are a good number of western universities/institutions offering ICT-based higher education successfully with quality for decades. ICT now changing the way of education in India and abroad, with the help of internet we can access anywhere anytime. Now in India also like western countries the higher education is becoming more advanced than before. The recent example is the commencement of online test for common admission test for management students. Other test like GMAT, GRE also held online as they are the higher-level quality exams.

ICR as a Value Developer: A Video Lesson Model

In the value developer approach, ICT is not a form of instruction just to learn from, but rather a tool for constructing values. There is a need for technology-content integration where in students are allowed more leeway to use and adopt ICT in their learning. Students can create their own multimedia knowledge representations that reflect their own perspectives on or understanding of ideas. Or students can collaborate with other students to develop ICT as their value base.

Conclusion:

The computer can store a vast amount of information but it cannot think. It will, therefore, be an anachronism to continue to use the human brain for memorizing information when it should be used for solving problems, creative thinking the skill attributes of knowledge workers. Therefore, any system of education unless it is learner centered, is around developing thinking skills and is able to help learners in acquiring the ability of learning how to learn will gradually lose its relevance.

Hence, the role of the teacher shall now be visualized by Sri Aurobindo as far back as in 1910. Empowering learners to develop ICT values is far more challenging than teaching a series of techniques in applications, which will soon be redundant in a fast changing context. We can use ICT not only as passive consumers and collectors of information, but also as people who are collaborative, creative and able to make critical choices. The ways in which we approach ICT values can be reflection of our own values and beliefs about what it means to learn and to teach in an information society. To conclude, the best and most effective teaching practice to empower the Learner is through developing ICT values among the learners.

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